

ISic0117

I.Sicily inscription 0117

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Original findspot unknown, first observed on a wall of the town hall of Termini

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 113

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 35.5 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth 12 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. []Popillio · P(ubli) · f(ilio) · Po[][(lia)(tribu)]

2. domo · Pollent[ia]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

...to Popillius, son of Publius, of the Pollia tribe(?)... from Pollentia...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285309

EDR 127538

EDCS 22100067

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49

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